

Assessment of engineered surfaces roughness by high-resolution 3D SEM photogrammetry

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Abstract

We describe a methodology to obtain three-dimensional models of engineered surfaces using scanning electron microscopy and multi-view photogrammetry (3DSEM). For the reconstruction of the 3D models of the surfaces we used freeware available in the cloud. The method was applied to study the surface roughness of metallic samples patterned with parallel grooves by means of laser. The results are compared with measurements obtained using stylus profilometry (PR) and SEM stereo-photogrammetry (SP). The application of 3DSEM is more time demanding than PR or SP, but it provides a more accurate representation of the surfaces. The results obtained with the three techniques are compared by investigating the influence of sampling step on roughness parameters.

Keywords: photogrammetry, 3DSEM, stereo-photogrammetry, profilometry, SEM metrology, patterned surfaces, roughness

1. Introduction

Design engineers have long known the relationship between surface texture and functional performance. For instance, with a controlled patterning of the surface, the engineer can enhance properties such as adhesion, paintability, friction, lubrication, reflectivity, or wear [Evans and Bryan, 1999; Persson *et al.*, 2005]. For controlling its fabrication, it is necessary to measure with accuracy the roughness of the surface, i.e., rugosity and waviness, typically using a combination of several characterization techniques, which can include stylus profilometry, optical microscopy, optical interferometry, laser probe rastering, scanning probe microscopy, or scanning electron microscopy. Each of these techniques has strengths and weaknesses. For instance, contact profilometry is the most widely used technique; it is simple and allows probing extended areas. On the other hand, the stylus tip radius precludes measurement of high

frequency structures and will distort sharp peaks and valleys frequently found in engineered surfaces. Likewise, stylus included angle limits slopes (aspect ratios) that can be measured [Evans and Bryan, 1999].

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) is the inspection 'work-horse' of the industry preparing structured surfaces. It provides images with excellent depth of focus and resolution - a very attractive combination for surfaces with high aspect ratios such as those frequently found in engineered surfaces. Conventional SEM is however, a long way from metrology because images are two-dimensional whereas for optimizing surface fabrication an accurate 3D representation (measuring the local depth) of the surface is critical. Over the past decades, many scientists have entered into the development of micro scale 3D characterization using SEM [Peddy and Collinson, 2014]. The most used technique is stereo-photogrammetry consisting on the acquisition of images of the surface of interest at two or three different low tilt angles, and after software processing a topographic map of the surface is obtained [Piazzesi, 1973; Boyde and Ross, 1975]. Single stereo-pair photogrammetry works well for relatively smooth surfaces with no occlusions [Raspanti *et al.*, 2005, Samak *et al.*, 2007; Chen *et al.*, 2012; Khokhlov *et al.*, 2012; Zolotukhin *et al.*, 2013; Limandri *et al.*, 2016]. However, the engineered surfaces like the ones shown in this work tend to be somewhat difficult to characterize: slopes and aspect ratios are high - compared with the average surface of engineering or material science interest. Hence, like in the case of profilometry, the low tilt angle used in stereo-photogrammetry limits slopes that can be measured.

Recent developments in photogrammetric algorithms can now provide 3D models of surfaces with high spatial resolution using an SEM (3DSEM). The algorithms extend conventional stereo-photogrammetry by combining not only 2 or 3 images, but many more images. The methods are reviewed in [Tafti *et al.*, 2015]. Some recent demonstrations of the methodology included the study of tribological properties of copper pins [Omrani *et al.*, 2016], the surface structure of biological samples [Eulitz and Reiss, 2015] and the distribution of catalysts particles [Gontard *et al.*, 2016].

The application of 3DSEM photogrammetry to patterned surfaces like the ones of interest in this work would require the acquisition of a large number of SEM images over a large tilt range, but the specimen stage of conventional SEMs can tilt only from -5 up to, at most, 70 degrees. First, we describe how to expand the effective maximum tilt range of any sample stage of a SEM, for the acquisition of sets of images suitable for multi-view 3DSEM photogrammetry. Next, we use the methodology for the reconstruction of high-resolution 3D models from series of SEM images of engineered surfaces patterned with parallel grooves. Also, we describe how to manipulate, calibrate and measure the 3D datasets to quantify standardized roughness parameters. Finally, we evaluate the accuracy of multi-view 3DSEM for metrological applications by comparing the measurements with those obtained using conventional profilometry and stereo-photogrammetry.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Samples

Three samples were investigated:

1. Sample A is a metallic reference (model PRN10 from the company Mahr) used to assess the reliability of the methodology developed in this paper.
2. Sample B is an AISI 304L stainless steel, irradiated using an Ytterbium fiber infrared pulsed laser of 1064 nm wavelength, model Rofin EasyMark F20, with an f-theta lens. Laser parameters were fixed at a power of 10 W, scanning speed of 50 mm/s, and repetition rate of 20 kHz. The texturing process produced parallel lines, with a distance between them of approximately 0.9 mm, aimed at increasing the hydrophobic properties of the surface.
3. Sample C is a Ti6Al4V alloy texturized in air and irradiated using the same laser as for sample B. Laser parameters were fixed at a power of 10 W, a scanning speed of 40 mm/s, and a repetition rate of 20 kHz. The texturing process produced parallel lines, with a distance between neighboring ones of approximately 0.12 mm.

2.2 3D SEM of planar samples: *an optimized geometry of acquisition of images*

In multi-view optical photogrammetry, collections of multiple photographs can be combined using robust algorithms to extract corresponding common features in image pairs of the series of images and to build a 3D point cloud of millions of surface points [Tomasi and Kanade, 1990; Hartely and Zisserman, 2004; Falkingham, 2012; Bemis et al., 2014]. The points are then triangulated to form a 3D mesh of the surface enclosing the volume of the object. The geometry of the object is established directly from uncalibrated images, i.e., without any prior information about the position of the camera.

Similarly, in 3DSEM, multiple overlapping SEM images taken from different perspectives around an object with the sample inclined at certain angles as shown in Figure 1a can be used to create accurate 3D models of the surface of samples [Tafti *et al.*, 2015; Eulitz and Reiss, 2015; Gontard *et al.*, 2016]. The secondary electron detector, SE, is at a fixed position and the sample is tilted and images of the object are acquired in sequence after successive in-plane rotations of $\Delta\phi$ degrees.

However, the geometry of acquisition used for 3DSEM of volumes is not directly applicable to planar surfaces like the ones of interest here. For instance, samples B (Fig.

4) and C (Fig. 5) display a periodic array of parallel grooves with large slopes. The bottom of the valleys and both sides of the walls of the grooves must be recorded from different viewpoints for a correct 3D reconstruction of their surfaces.

But if the sample is tilted at high α -tilt angles using the geometry of acquisition described in Figure 1a and then it is rotated in-plane, the valleys of the grooves will be occluded by the peaks at certain orientations, and 3D reconstruction of the surface will fail. If the α -tilt angle is sufficiently low for recording the bottom of the valleys of the grooves then when performing the in-plane rotation of 360°, some information of the walls will be missing. Also, consecutive images may be too similar (the sample texture is highly symmetric) and the software will not be able to separate corresponding feature points in different image pairs.

Figure 1b describes an optimized acquisition geometry for the application of 3D SEM to surfaces that circumvents the strong constraints (i.e., high slopes) imposed by the structure of the patterned surfaces. The surfaces shown in Figures 3 and 4 are periodic in the direction perpendicular to the direction of the grooves. Therefore, instead of using the general geometry of acquisition shown in Fig. 1a, we used the geometry of conventional stereo-photogrammetry. And instead of using just one single pair of images as in stereo-photogrammetry, we acquired multiple images of the surfaces using a large range of tilts symmetrically around the zero tilt position of the sample stage (see Fig. 1b).

In most SEM microscopes the tilt range of the sample stage does not cover the large tilt range needed for our approach. Typically, the stage can be tilted from a small negative value up to a large positive angle (e.g., α -tilt range from -5 to 90°). We have devised a method to overcome this limitation that allows the acquisition of SEM images in a wide symmetrical range of negative and positive tilt angles, in any SEM. The individual steps followed the next sequence:

1. The samples were fixed onto an SEM pin mount and scanned until an appropriate area close to a corner-defining boundary was found. This will break the symmetry of the pattern and will improve the matching between pairs of images.
2. The sample was rotated in-plane until the grooves were parallel to the tilt axis.
3. A partial series of images was acquired between 0 and +45° in steps of 5°, and saved with names following consecutive numbers from 10 to 19 (Fig. 1b, step 2).
4. As the sample was tilted in successive 5° increments, the image was centered manually by moving the stage in the x- and y-axes to approximately recenter the field of view. Focus was manually adjusted for consistency between micrographs, using the same structure in each image. At high tilt angles the magnification of

the sample can change due to variations of the eucentric height. The magnification may be kept consistent in each captured image of the tilt series by changing the Z-axis position as required. But it is not necessary to keep high precision in correcting this change. Unlike conventional stereo-photogrammetry software, the freeware used here is designed to work with uncalibrated images and effectively handles changes in magnification.

5. When the image at $+45^\circ$ was acquired, the sample was rotated in-plane by 180° (Fig. 1b, step 3).
6. A second partial series of images from $+45^\circ$ to $+5^\circ$ in steps of 5° was acquired and the images were saved with consecutive numbers from 1 to 9 (Fig. 1b, step 4).
7. In order to have a consistent tilt series, the series of images 1 to 9 (acquired from $+45$ to 5 degrees) were imported into the software ImageJ as an image sequence (Import -> Image sequence) and then rotated 180° (Image -> Transform -> Rotate 90° > Rotate 90° or alternatively Flip vertically -> Flip horizontally) and saved again as an image sequence without changing the names.

As a result of this processing the full series of images from 1 to 19 displays a continuous tilt of the surface from -45 to $+45$ degrees.

The tilt series used for reconstructing the 3D models of sample A was acquired using a SEM Hitachi SUI510. The tilt series used for reconstructing the 3D model of samples B and C were acquired using a FEI Quanta SEM. Both SEMs were operated with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV and the working distance was adjusted in each case to have a suitable field-of-view. Images with sizes of 1024×943 pixels were recorded with the SE detector and finally saved in *bmp* format. After converting the images to *jpeg* format the entire datasets were loaded into the freeware 123DCatch. A more detailed explanation of the 3D reconstruction and visualization procedure can be found in [Gontard LC *et al.*, 2016].

2.3 Roughness parameters

2.3.1 Using 3DSEM

We exported the 3D surface models into files with *xyz* format using the freeware Meshlab. This format is a plain text file with three columns corresponding to the *x*, *y* and *z* coordinates of each of the corners of the triangles that made up the triangular mesh of vertex and faces of the 3D model of the surface. The *xyz* file was then read and processed with Matlab software. The point cloud (x_i, y_i, z_i) points of the mesh was rotated in 3D space until the patterned surface was parallel to the *xy* coordinates plane and with the grooves of the sample oriented parallel to the *x*-direction. Next, from the point cloud the continuous surface (3D mesh in Figures 2c, 3c, 4c and 5c) was recalculated using the Matlab function *TriScatteredInterp(x,y,z)*. The surface was then reprojected in the *z*-direction to obtain an elevation map or 2D heights map (Figures 2d, 3d, 4d and 5d). Finally, aiming at quantifying the rugosity of the surfaces, height profiles (also called primary profiles or P-profiles in the field of metrology of surfaces) were measured along the *y*-direction perpendicular to the grooves and integrated along the *x*-width of an area contained within the elevation map (rectangles in white color in Figures 2d, 3d, 4d and 5d).

R-profiles (see Figures 3g, 4g and 5g) were calculated as the deviation of the P-profiles respect to the mean lines of the P-profiles (R-profile = P-profile - mean line). The mean lines shown in Figures 3f, 4f and 5f were calculated smoothing iteratively (between 500 and 1200 times) each P-profile using a mean average filter with a span of 5 pixels for each point. For calculation of the R-profiles we discarded the first and last 5 pixels of the mean line because this type of filtering introduces artifacts at the beginning and at the end of the curves. The surfaces were calibrated multiplying the coordinates of the point cloud by a factor such as the peak separation in the R-profiles coincided with the distance between grooves measured on the calibrated SEM images acquired at zero tilt. Finally, R_a , R_q and R_z values were measured on the averaged R-profiles using the definitions of the UNE-EN ISO 4287 standard (see Supporting Information).

For calculating the curves shown in Figure 6 showing roughness parameters as a function of sampling interval, L_s , P-profiles were measured at *x*-positions separated by L_s and binned in the *y*-direction by an amount given by $x\text{-width} / L_s$.

2.3.2 Using Profilometry

Roughness profiles of sample A, B and C were measured using a Perthometer from the company Mahr. R_a , R_q and R_z were calculated following the UNE-EN ISO 4287 standard (see definitions in Supporting Information) averaging the measurements of four R-profiles measured with an evaluation length of 2.5 mm, a total length of 7.5 mm and $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$.

2.3.3 Using Stereophotogrammetry

A pair of SEM images were acquired at 0 and at -15 degrees' tilt in a (FEG)SEM Nova NanoSEM 450 operated at 20 kV. The heights map of Figure 5 was obtained using the software MountainsMap®SEM from the company Digital Surf. R_a , R_q , R_z were measured on the averaged R-profile of Fig. 5g calculated as explained in paragraph 2.3.1.

3. Results

3.1 Reliability of 3DSEM models for 3D metrology

In order to check that the 3D models of the surfaces obtained using the methodology explained before are reliable for metrological applications we compared the results of measuring a metallic reference pattern (sample A in this work) using profilometry and 3DSEM (Fig. 2a).

We found in our experiment that when 3DSEM photogrammetry is used on a planar surface, only the central portions of the field-of-view used during the acquisition of the images is reconstructed accurately. The explanation for this is that experiments were performed at low magnification and when the samples were tilted to high angles, the parts of the images far from the tilt axis became out-of-focus. As a result, the 3D models were deformed close to the boundaries of the field-of-view. In order to estimate the roughness parameters of sample A only the area inside the white square shown in Fig 2d was used.

The R-profile measured using the 3DSEM model fits well with the R-profile (dashed line) measured using contact profilometry (Fig. 2e). Both curves coincide in shape and their roughness parameters are comparable (summarized in Table 1). The curve in the case of the 3DSEM profile is noisier (indicating that the surface is not flat in the short scales) and the minimum and maximum peaks are slightly rounded what is indicative of the higher resolution achievable with the 3DSEM technique.

3.2 3DSEM metrology of rugosity of surfaces patterned with grooves

Figure 3 shows the results of measuring the roughness parameters of sample B. Figure 3a is a representative SEM image from the tilt series used for reconstructing the 3D model of Fig. 3b, which is shown as a 3D mesh in Figure 3c. The P-profile in Fig. 3d was measured inside the white square box in Fig. 3b with a sampling step $L_s = 2 \mu\text{m}$. The R-profile in Figure 3e was calculated as the deviation of the P-profile from the mean line. From the R-profile, the following roughness values could be retrieved: $R_a = 4.47 \mu\text{m}$, $R_q =$

5.26 μm , $R_z = 19.4 \mu\text{m}$ and $S_m = 90 \mu\text{m}$. Sample B was measured also using profilometry (see the measured curves in Supporting Information). The roughness values obtained using both techniques, with the same sampling step of 8 μm , are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 4 shows the results of measuring the roughness parameters of sample C. Figure 4a is a representative SEM image from the tilt series used for reconstructing the 3D model of Fig. 4b, which is shown as a 3D mesh in Figure 4c. The R-profile in Fig. 4g was measured inside the white box of the heights map shown in Fig 4d with a sampling step of 5 μm . From the R-profile, the following roughness values were estimated: $R_a = 19.1 \mu\text{m}$, $R_q = 21.77 \mu\text{m}$, $R_z = 75.7 \mu\text{m}$ and $S_m = 123.7 \mu\text{m}$. The same sample was measured using profilometry (see the measured curves in Supporting Information). The values obtained using both techniques, with $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$, are summarized in Table 1.

3.3 Stereophotogrammetry versus multi-view 3DSEM

We compared also the results of roughness of sample C measured using 3DSEM and the more conventional approach of using stereophotogrammetry. Figure 5 shows the 3D surface reconstruction performed on sample C, but using only one stereo-pair of images. The model is not a true 3D model of the surface but an elevation map, and does not contain any information about the intensities of the texture, in contrast with the 3D models shown in Figs 2, 3 and 4. The map in Fig. 5b is not smooth, with multiple spikes of different height scattered across the entire surface and that are not present neither in the real sample nor in the 3D model shown in Fig. 4b. From the R-profile shown in Fig. 5g the calculated roughness parameters were $R_a = 21.9 \mu\text{m}$, $R_q = 24.2 \mu\text{m}$, $R_z = 70.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $S_m = 133 \mu\text{m}$, with $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 1. Measurements of several parameters of rugosity of samples A, B and C using 3DSEM, stereo-photogrammetry (SP) and a stylus profilometer (PR). x: no measurement. Sampling step, $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$.

Params.	Sample A			Sample B		Sample C		
	Nominal values	PR	3DSEM	PR	3DSEM	PR	3DSEM	SP
R_a (μm)	2.5	2.46	2.47	4.77	4.47	13.7	19.1	21.9
R_q (μm)	x	x	x	x	5.26	x	21.77	24.2
R_z (μm)	10	10.26	9.7	28.79	19.4	86.01	75.7	81
R_{sm} (μm)	>130	139.1	139	x	90	x	123.7	133

3.4 Comparison of 3DSEM, stereo-photogrammetry and profilometry

It appears convenient to discuss the differences of contact profilometry (PR), stereophotogrammetry (SP) and 3DSEM. At this respect, it is useful to study the dependence of the techniques on a suitable scaling factor [Poon and Bhushan, 1995; Szyszka *et al.*, 2016]. Figure 6 shows the effect of sampling step, L_s , on the roughness parameters. The top row corresponds to the values of R_a , R_q and R_z of sample B using 3DSEM. The bottom row gathers curves of sample C using 3DSEM and SP. The values of R_a and R_z measured with PR, at a fixed $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$, are also indicated.

The values obtained from 3DSEM increase with L_s until a maximum is reached at values of 4-6 μm . In contrast, the curves using SP are more flat and converge towards 3DSEM for larger L_s . These different trends may be understood by considering that the surface model reconstructed using SP is oversampled at small values of L_s , and the heights' map is randomly populated with spikes that are not real (Figs. 5b and 5c), which in turn increase the average roughness heights. When L_s is larger the spikes are averaged out, the surface becomes smoother and the values of roughness decrease. In contrast, 3DSEM provides a true high-resolution model of the surface and, therefore, it is expected that the roughness value is proportional to L_s , and also that the smaller the value L_s the more accurate the roughness value will be.

Figure 6 shows also that the values measured using PR (with $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$) can deviate up to a 33% respect to those measured using 3DSEM and SP (see for example the value of R_z of sample B). This deviation of R_z may be explained because the R-profiles measured using 3DSEM and SP were calculated from R-profiles obtained averaging a large number of P-profiles and not using the standardized conditions for PR. Unlike the R-profile of PR, 3DSEM and SP R-profiles are smoothed versions of individual line profiles. Therefore, it is expected that when L_s increases, smoothing increases and R_a and R_z will decrease.

Figure 6 shows a large deviation of R_a of sample C. Our interpretation here is that 3DSEM and SP have better spatial resolution than PR and therefore roughness measurements are expected to be more accurate. For PR, the ability to reproduce the original surface features depends strongly on the finite dimensions of the stylus tip. The smaller the stylus size, the closer it will follow the original profile. Also, the stylus tip is in fixed orientation respect to the surface and cannot measure surface details at the steep-sided walls of the grooves. These differences are evident if one compares the roughness profiles of sample C shown in the Supporting information with the image and the profiles provided by 3DSEM in Figure 4.

Conclusions

We have described a methodology to acquire series of images in a range of angles that duplicates symmetrically around the zero tilt the maximum tilt range of the stage of a conventional scanning electron microscope (SEM). Using this methodology, multi-view photogrammetry using SEM (3DSEM) was applied for reconstructing 3D models of the surfaces of two laser-engineered samples patterned with parallel grooves were reconstructed. From the models of the surfaces three roughness parameters R_a , R_z and R_q were measured and compared with the values obtained with conventional stereophotogrammetry, and contact profilometry. Deviations on the measured values using the three techniques were observed. The differences arise firstly, because the averaged roughness profiles measured from 3DSEM data are smoother than those measured using stereophotogrammetry or profilometry. Secondly, the surfaces examined here present high slopes and 3DSEM must provide a more accurate representation of the surface under study.

The 3D models of the samples displayed artifacts at the boundaries of the field-of-view used for acquiring the series of images. For this reason, the measurements of roughness were limited to smaller regions located near the center of the field-of-view. The freeware used for multi-view 3DSEM in this work has the advantage that is readily available in the cloud of internet. It is designed to work with images acquired using mobile optical cameras and can handle uncalibrated images, i.e., the software can work without any prior input on the magnification or the angles used for acquiring the images. This is an advantage for mobile applications but it is a limitation for 3DSEM because it does not make use of relevant information such as the tilt angles that are perfectly characterized in a typical experiment performed in an SEM. Certainly, the use of this information could speed up and increase the fidelity of the reconstruction of the 3D model. Nonetheless, 3DSEM is a field that is growing fast and tools are being developed specifically for the peculiarities of SEM. This is the case, for example, of the tool 3DSEM++ [Tafti, et al., 2015, 2016], which is described as adaptive and intelligent by including advanced computational technologies, such as machine learning. Certainly, the availability of these algorithms and programs either freeware or integrated in commercial software will become part of the toolbox for the metrology of surfaces in the micro- and nanoscale. In this context, this contribution provides methodologies and experimental strategies to collect the necessary initial set of image data of planar surfaces.

Although at present the processing time for the acquisition and reconstruction of 3DSEM surfaces is relatively long compared with other techniques it provides three-dimensional information with high-resolution that is out of reach for any other metrological technique.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. (a) Illustration of the acquisition of images in multi-view SEM photogrammetry (3DSEM) for the three-dimensional reconstruction of the surface of an object. The object is fixed in one position and the images are acquired from different viewpoints (changing position and tilt axis of the camera) around the sample. (b) Methodology used in this work for the application of 3DSEM to reconstruct high-resolution 3D models of patterned surfaces. (c) Flowchart for the acquisition with high-tilt angles of a series of images symmetrically around the zero tilt. (d) View of the patterned sample B located inside a Quanta SEM.

Figure 2. (a) 3D model (mesh and texture of intensities) of the sample A reconstructed with 3DSEM from 19 SEM images and freeware photogrammetry software. The model is a realistic 3D surface enhanced by the combination of the 3D mesh of the surface wrapped with the texture of SE intensities of the original images. Sample A is a metallic reference sample PRN-10 from Mahr with the following specifications: Triangular profile, R_a approx. $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, R_z approx. $10 \mu\text{m}$ and $S_m > 130 \mu\text{m}$. (b) R-profile of the same sample measured using contact profilometry: $R_a = 2.46 \mu\text{m}$, $R_z = 10.26 \mu\text{m}$, $S_m = 139.1 \mu\text{m}$. (c) 3D mesh of the 3D model shown in (a). The colors indicate different heights. (d) Heights map or projection of the surface mesh along the z-direction. (e) The dashed line is a detail of the R-profile shown in (b) using the profilometer. The solid line (in red color) is the R-profile measured from the heights map along the y-direction and integrated along the x-direction of the area boxed in white in (d).

Figure 3. (a) Representative 2D SEM image of sample B acquired at a tilt of 30°. (b) 3D model (mesh and texture of intensities) of sample C with 95779 vertices and 191313 faces reconstructed with 3DSEM from 19 SEM images and freeware photogrammetry software. The model is a realistic 3D surface enhanced by the combination of the 3D mesh of the surface wrapped with the texture of SE intensities of the original images. (c) 3D mesh of the model shown in (b) used for the measurements of rugosity. (d) Projection of the surface in z-direction. (e) Histograms of heights inside the white square shown in (d) with an x-width = 450 μm and y-height = 370 μm. (f) P-profile (thick black line) integrated along the x-direction with $L_s = 2$ μm. The mean line (thin blue line) was calculated applying iteratively 500 times a mean average filter with a span of 5 pixels. (g) Average R-profile of the surface.

Figure 4. (a) 2D SEM image of sample C at zero tilt. The inset inside the black square shows a magnified region of the sample. (b) 3D model (mesh and texture of intensities) of sample C with 5740 vertices and 10725 faces reconstructed with 3DSEM from 19 SEM images and freeware photogrammetry software. The model is a realistic 3D surface enhanced by the combination of the 3D mesh of the surface wrapped with the texture of SE intensities of the original images. (c) 3D mesh of the model shown in (b) used for the measurements of rugosity. (d) Projection of the surface in z-direction. (e) Histograms of heights inside the white square shown in (d) with an x-width = 942 μm and y-height = 595 μm . (f) P-profile (thick black line) integrated along the x-direction with $L_s = 5 \mu\text{m}$. The mean line (thin blue line) was calculated applying iteratively 1000 times a mean average filter with a span of 5 pixels. (g) Average R-profile of the surface.

Figure 5. (a) Illustration of the acquisition of images in an SEM for 3DSEM reconstruction of planar surfaces using a single stereo-pair and commercial software. (b) 3D elevation map (mesh) of the surface of sample C using two images acquired with 0 and +15 degrees' tilt respectively. The mesh contains 998400 vertices and 1992804 faces (c) 3D mesh of the elevation map. (c) 3D mesh of the model shown in (b). (d) Projection of the surface in z-direction. (e) Histograms of heights inside the white square shown in (c) with an x-width = 1120 μm and y-height = 710 μm . (f) P-profile (thick black line) integrated along the x-direction. The mean line (thin blue line) was calculated applying iteratively 1200 times a mean average filter with a span of 5 pixels. (g) Average R-profile of the surface.

Figure 6. Top row, roughness parameters R_a , R_q and R_z of sample B measured using 3DSEM as a function of the sampling step. Bottom row, roughness parameters R_a , R_q and R_z of sample C measured using 3DSEM and stereo-photogrammetry, SP, as a function of sampling step, L_s . The points with diamond shape are the averaged values measured using contact profilometry, PR, with $L_s = 8 \mu\text{m}$, and the vertical bars indicate the range of values measured (see Supporting Information).

Supporting information

Assessment of engineered surfaces roughness by high-resolution 3D SEM photogrammetry

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Definitions of parameters for rugosity (Standard UNE-EN ISO 4287)

- **Roughness average Ra** is the arithmetic average of the absolute values of the roughness profile ordinates:

$$R_a = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |z_i|$$

with n the number of points and z_i the profile ordinates at point i .

- **Root mean square (RMS) roughness Rq** is the root mean square average of the roughness profile ordinates:

$$R_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n z_i^2}$$

being n the number of sampling lengths.

- **Mean roughness depth Rz** is the arithmetic mean value of the single roughness depths R_{zi} of consecutive sampling lengths:

$$R_z = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n R_{zi}$$

being n the number of sampling lengths.

- **Mean width of profile elements Rsm** is the arithmetic mean value of the widths of profile elements of the roughness profile. A profile element consists of a profile peak and an adjacent profile valley:

$$R_{sm} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |S_{mi}|$$

Contact profilometry of Sample B

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	5,19	µm
Rz	30,98	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	4,74	µm
Rz	28,16	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	4,72	µm
Rz	30,58	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	4,43	µm
Rz	25,43	µm

Contact profilometry of Sample C

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	12,89	µm
Rz	80,48	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	13,23	µm
Rz	71,65	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	13,73	µm
Rz	81,21	µm

LS	8,0	µm
LT	7,50	mm
LM	2,50	mm
Z	1	
VB	±250,0	µm
NX	4800	

Ra	14,66	µm
Rz	110,71	µm